

PLANET4B - understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

Case “Trade and global value chains”

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Findings from photography-based workshop with Stakeholder Board (SB)
Workshop held on 25 & 28 June 2024

*Workshop participants are anonymised in this report

Introductory notes

We designed a 2h photography-based workshop with the case study Stakeholder Board, following the “**Methodology Guide for Task 3.2**” (**Systems mapping and transformative interventions**), provided by the task leader CzechGlobe, in the context of the Horizon Europe PLANET4B Project¹.

We hosted the workshop twice, with two different groups of Stakeholder Board (SB)² members. One application was held in English (in June 25, 2-4pm CEST) and another in Portuguese (in June 28, 2-4pm CEST), for the following reasons. First, to accommodate the SB members’ busy schedules and different locations (some in Brazil and others in the Netherlands), which prevented us from finding a single date where all members were available. Second, to provide an inclusive space, as some members are non-English speakers.

Table 1. Information about the SB workshops

¹ More information on this project can be found here: <https://planet4b.eu/>

² In PLANET4B, each sector-based case study has a Stakeholder Board (SB). The board “collaborates closely with cases during their research, paying attention to the particularities of local communities, sectoral stakeholders, policy actors, business decision-makers, intersectionality dimensions, and vulnerable social groups” connected to the case study research (Mendes et al., 2023, p.2). In the case study “Trade and global value chains”, we adopted a fluid composition for the SB. This allows us to include new SB members in any stage of the case development. For more information, see: Mendes, V., Kelemen, E., Inoue, C. Y. A., Aas-Hanssen, A. E., Barton, D., Bolsø, R. ... & Villa, M. (2023a). Learning Communities and sectoral Advisory Boards established for 5 intensive place-based and 6 extensive sector-based case studies (Report No D3.1). Project 101082212 – PLANET4B. Brussels: European Research Executive Agency. Available https://planet4b.eu/wpcontent/uploads/2023/12/PLANET4B_D3.1_Establishing_LearningCommunities.pdf.

Date of application	June 25, 2-4pm CEST	June 28, 2-4pm CEST
Language	Portuguese	English
Participants	1 NGO (Netherlands) 2 Local community (Brazil) 2 Academia (1 Brazil, 1 Netherlands) Total: 5	1 NGO (Netherlands) 3 Academia (1 Brazil, 2 Netherlands) Total: 4
Stories	A to E	F to H
Resources	Power Point Teams Miro Board	Power Point Teams Miro Board

The activity was held online through *Microsoft Teams*. During the sessions, we used *Microsoft Power Point* and a *Miro Board*, which we prepared in advance. Dates and time were selected via a poll in the *Framadate* platform. Previously to the workshop, we invited each participant to select a photograph, and based on it tell us a personal story which would inspire a change/intervention to improve the situation of biodiversity and people along the beef and/or soy trade routes between Brazil and the Netherlands. We used the following prompt (English version) in the invitation e-mail:

Box 1. Prompt sent weeks before the workshop, inviting SB members to prepare a story

A photograph and a story

We ask you to select a photograph (personal, or from the Internet without copyright). Starting from this photo, share with us a story of up to 5 minutes. The story must somehow connect your personal experiences/identity to biodiversity loss along the soy and/or beef chain, Brazil-EU/Netherlands. If you prefer not to tell a personal story, feel free to use your imagination and invent one.

The idea is that, through personal stories from your everyday life, or from work, from the research you do, or from experiences that you have lived and would like to share (identity & experiences), you propose a change that can improve the situation of biodiversity and people in some (or both) of the soy and beef supply chains between Brazil and the Netherlands. The story will help us reflect on a central aspect in PLANET4B: how our identities, lived/personal experiences (oppression, privileges, etc.) connect to our decision-making (directly or indirectly) that eventually lead to biodiversity loss along these supply chains.

In your story, indicate actions/interventions that could lead us to the suggested change.

Indicators of change

We would also ask you to prepare a list of 2 to 3 indicators for each action/intervention identified. Indicators that can be used to track/monitor the change. Please send us the actions/interventions in .docx or pptx. until the date of the meeting (simple bullets, for example).

Broader impacts

Finally, describe which potential broader impacts (reaching other sectors, other geographies, etc.) could occur if the change becomes a reality. What barriers would exist to prevent these broader impacts? And what

opportunities can catalyze such impacts? Please send us this material in written format, in a .docx or pptx., until the date of the meeting (bullets, short paragraphs, etc.)

During the workshop (Table 2), participants granted us permission to record all sessions. Records were transcribed automatically by *Teams*. The remaining parts of this document are based on such transcripts, the notes produced by participants in the Miro Board during the sessions, as well as written material that some participants sent to us previously to the workshop.

Table 2. Workshop sessions

Sessions	Time	Tools
Introduction (10 min) (welcome, rationale of workshop)	2:00 – 2:10	ppt
Stories, interventions, narratives of change (30 min stories; 20 min Miro) (pictures, stories, interventions, leverage points)	2:10 – 3:00	Pictures, Miro, Plenary
Break (5 min!)		
Monitoring change through indicators (15 min) (indicators for the chosen interventions)	3:05 – 3:20	Miro, Plenary
Broader impacts (15 min) (other sectors and policies, opportunities and barriers)	3:20 – 3:40	Miro, Plenary
Wrap up (25 min) (debate key outcomes)	3:40 – 4:00	Plenary

Below, we present and reflect upon the findings. Although we had 9 participants, only 8 stories were shared, because one participant only joined in a later stage during the workshop.

Photographs & Stories

Story A. Children and rural development in Brazil’s Cerrado biome. Concretely, more access to companies’ sourcing polygons. On a deeper level, the development of rural areas through alternative production systems.

Picture 1. Children in an area of soybeans expansion in the Brazilian Cerrado biome. Photo credit: Tiago Foresti.

*“This photo, in fact, was taken during fieldwork that I did. It's about the expansion of soybeans in the Cerrado, and the displacement, the expulsion of local communities. This was an experience that I had during this fieldwork. It became very clear to me what the communities call **silent expulsion**. And it's often made invisible. The picture always brings me a lot of joy, because **it makes me think about two changes, on two levels**, which I think are very necessary. I'm going to talk about a very pragmatic change and another change, which is more abstract, let's say, more optimistic, holistic.*

*The **pragmatic change**, especially in the context of the European Union Deforestation Regulation (EUDR), in implementing this legislation, and enable it in general, is perhaps, ideally so, very optimistic. I think it would be great if we had **more access to companies' sourcing polygons**, because we talk a lot about traceability and how to monitor? And we are able to do this on a national scale, even on a local scale, but we never know exactly where the companies are buying from, because only they have these origination polygons and they are not obliged to make this transparent to the civil society at the moment, only for governments. What if we had some way of adding anonymization to these polygons, so that we could also monitor and verify that what they are saying makes sense in reality? According to the data we have, I think it would be very positive.*

*And then, **a more abstract change**. So, the change in values would actually be more holistic, right?*

*Understanding that it is not just soy that brings development, benefits, value to life, or even happiness, connecting with the photo, right? We need to understand that **there are other ways for us to develop**, to continue using this mainstream vocabulary. **This is to develop rural areas of Brazil through the alternative systems proposed by these local communities**, which are so often displaced by soybeans and by livestock farming.”*

(SB member from Academia & Environmental NGO)

Story B. Macaws in urban Brasília, visitors or victims from habitat loss? *Chapada dos Veadeiros* national park and soy plantations “right on the edge” of the protected area.

Picture 2. Macaws in an urban area of Brasília, in the Cerrado. Photo credit: workshop participant.

“I actually had a hard time choosing just one, so I’ll quickly share two pictures. First, it’s this wonderful macaw in my garden. (...) I live in Brasília, Lago Norte and this macaw, a bunch of them, comes to visit me often. This other photo that I share is from a field trip here in the Alto Paraíso region. It’s in Chapada dos Veadeiros national park (state of Goiás, in Cerrado), and here we see a soybean plantation. Soybeans right on the edge of the park, right?”

Picture 3. Soy plantations nearby the *Chapada dos Veadeiros* National Park in the Brazilian Cerrado. Photo credit: workshop participant.

*This is always what I see, it is a personal story. In a personal impression, whenever the macaws are here, I'm super happy. Joyful! But at the same time, I'm always asking myself questions, I've asked several people this, but no one has been able to answer me clearly. Are these macaws here because they cannot survive in the rural area around Brasília, in the Cerrado, because this area is taken over by soybeans? My question is: **how can we protect this biodiversity in the Cerrado biome?** Of course, **I don't want them not to be in Brasília either, but I'd like to know if they are being protected, the macaws, the toucans, throughout the region here in the Cerrado. (...)***

*The first time I've been there was in 1998 and now, last year (2023), I was there again and came across this area taken over by soybeans. And talking to some small producers around the park, they are also concerned about **the impacts of large production as regards to the use of agrochemicals.** These small producers want to carry out agroecological production. But they are not able to do it because of the soybean problem next door.*

*So, I proposed some changes. It is comprehensive, I think, perhaps too comprehensive here for this case, but it would be **valuing the preservation of vegetation, native vegetation, biodiversity, expansion of forest reserves, protected areas or even restoration. It's in the region.***

*But, talking here initially with you (during the workshop), is in terms of values. I thought we could **value rural tourism a little more, ecological tourism as a way of protecting these areas as well.**"*

(SB member from Academia)

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Story C. Mobilizing against trade agreements that support large scale farming. Moving towards agroecology and food sovereignty.

Picture 4. Farmers protesting against the EU-Mercosur Free Trade Agreement, in the EU Commission headquarters, in Brussels.

*“I would like to share two images as well. One of them was taken a few months ago. It is the farmers protests in Brussels in which we from La Via Campesina also played a part in mobilizing farmers to come. **One of the big demands here is to stop the EU-Mercosur Free Trade Agreement.**”*

Picture 5. Farmers adopting an agroecological production system in the Netherlands.
 Note: we covered peoples' faces in the pic for the sake of anonymization.

*And then the second is a picture of a new farmers in the Netherlands. They are two young farmers that have taken over a conventional farm. They are called Simone and Matias (fictitious names). They are also one of the members of our organization, La Via Campesina. The farm used to be a conventional farm. But they took it over and **they want to move to a more agroecological type of farming system.***

*And what does it mean a conventional farm here in the Netherlands? It is a dairy farm, right? So, with cattle. The conventional farm typically produces a lot of milk. It's very intensive, it uses a lot of feed from soy to produce this milk. And they depend also on **a type of cattle called Holstein Friesian, which are quite famous Dutch cattle variety that produces a lot of milk.** But also, these cattle need really a lot of feed to function properly. The Holstein Friesian cattle also depend on what is called **English ryegrass, which is a type of grass. That is grown in a monoculture, right? It's very rich grass. It also requires a lot of chemical fertilizers to grow well.** Uh, so this is the model of conventional farming in the Netherlands.*

*To move towards agroecological farming, and that's what these farmers are trying to do, they need to switch to, **they want to switch to, more diverse grassland.** So not only have this English ryegrass. But also **integrate diverse herbs and trees and herbs.** In addition, **they need to introduce a different type of cattle.** And to make other changes on the farm.*

*But the difficulty for them were the following. First, **it was very difficult for them to take over the farm. No bank wants to invest in a farm that is moving away from conventional farming.** They had to look for many small loans. And, in the end, they had 13 different parties giving them small loans so that they could buy the farm*

*A second difficulty was the issue of production, right? **The price of milk is very low. They want to start also produce feed for themselves, right? Rather than importing.** And, to overcome this, they made small start to sell directly for small shops where they sell the milk and cheese. But still, they're struggling a lot. So, this transition to agriculture is very difficult.*

The changes that I would like to propose are. First, a reform of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). We need to be able to reregulate markets better and ensure that there is a minimum price for farmers. And ensure that this type of money is put in towards transition towards agroecology rather than supporting large scale agriculture. Second, we also want to stop with free trade agreements, stop with the EU-Mercosur agreement. And reconsider other free trade agreements, both in the Netherlands and in the global South, so that farmers and the people can move towards more system of food sovereignty.”

(SB member from Academia & Environmental NGO)

Story D. Amazon schoolteachers and students poisoned by soy agrottoxins. Cattle farming amid a lonely Chesnutt tree, “as if the tree could live without the forest that surrounds it.” We need another type of involvement with the forest!

Picture 6. Belterra in Santarém, Pará state, in the Brazilian Amazon.

“Okay, this is a first photo. As you can see, we have some cattle there. It is in Belterra, a city close to Santarem (Pará state, in the Amazon). I believe it is very symbolic, because it represents the two spaces, both the advance of livestock farming and the advance of soybeans in the region.

*There is a very powerful life story that happened the week before last week, when I was chosen to teach a class at a school (where I already minister some courses), because the teacher had been ill. We didn't know what had exactly happened, but we found out that she felt ill (...). **She had been ill as***

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a matter of fact because of agricultural pesticides. (...) Three teachers had nausea, headaches and so on. If I'm not mistaken, a number of around 60 students were also affected. This is even being discussed here by the state Public Ministry, and people are filing a lawsuit against the responsible companies. This is a fact that unfortunately recurs at this school. This is not the first time that this has happened.

So, the space is being greatly devastated. I had the opportunity to visit Santarém at the end of the 1990s. Since then, the Belterra region has been completely transformed. What I highlight is that sometimes we look at that tree there in the background of the picture. It is probably a chestnut tree, and I don't think it's anything else. I cannot find anything that is as stupid as human laws that say that you have to keep a chestnut tree standing, because it is an ancient tree, etc., but you have to destroy all the nature around it. As if the chestnut tree could live without the forest that surrounds it.

Picture 7. Belterra in Santarém, Pará state, in the Brazilian Amazon.

*Well, the second image is also in Belterra, which is called plateau. On the other side, there is a community. (...). The Indigenous people Kumaruara. (...) In some way, it is **a hope that we can think about another involvement with the forest that is not just exploitation**. Because this model that we created has really affected communities, right? Polluting the soil, damaging the water. Not to mention the mining activity as well, which is another activity that you see in the river. The river is also being impacted by the illegal exploitation.”*

(SB member from Local community & Academia)

Story E. Environmental racism. “When Cargill operations were set up in the Santarém region (Brazilian Amazon), they destroyed the local beach called *Vera Paz*,” a space for popular leisure activities. They argued that it was “a beach for the poor, black, and vagabond.” This shows how agribusiness’ “rational logic of development” is actually “racist, violent, genocidal,” aiming to clear the territory to open up the space for soy monocultures. [No picture was presented in this story]

“Hey guys. I am Maíke Kumaruara. A Black man from the Amazon. A Black man from the Earth. A fighter for social justice, for environmental justice. I wanted to take advantage of this opportunity, and I am grateful for this opportunity, to publicize our struggle. To extend a bond of solidarity. This is very important for us. (...) I really wanted to send you some photos, some photos that in principle we cannot publish because there are children scratching themselves, children getting sick because of poison spraying. But there are others that I can reveal, from a school surrounded by soybean plantations. This is important for us.

I usually say that we are on the frontier of global agribusiness. The tropical forests in other spaces, in Asia, for example, are already gone. We still have ours here (reference to the Amazon), which still has 75% of the forest standing. But we are surrounded. Santarém is a great centre of resistance. (...) The Tapajós is a soy trade route. The Yanomami miners are there in Itaituba and continue to throw a lot of mercury into the river. And here in this region of the Santarém Plateau it is soybeans, trying to move forward, trying to advance into Indigenous lands and Quilombola territories.

*One of the ways through which soy farmers advance is the practice of environmental racism. It doesn't matter if we are Indigenous communities, rural workers, Quilombola communities, they (reference to soy agribusiness) continue to contaminate the soil. They continue spraying agrotoxins close to communities. And this has a violent impact on the communities. They have no concerns. **We have a teacher who is resisting, right? At a school. She made a complaint, but the police officer was very strict, he said: “Either we get rid of the school or of the soy farmer, right?” So, large soy farmers’ economic power is imposed. And we have to fight for schools to remain. This is emblematic.***

*And then, something else to close. It is very symbolic, right? **When Cargill settled here, it destroyed a popular beach called Vera Paz. And the idea was that it was a poor man's beach. A beach for black people, for thieves, a vagabonds’ beach. But it was practically the only leisure space for the working population not located in the city centre.***

I am not going to talk about the archaeological cemetery, because public opinion didn't think it was important either, but it (Cargill port operations) was built on top of the archaeological cemetery.

*I found here that this symbolism is what they endorse. **They justify the alleged white racial superiority of agribusiness, which is said to be superior, in a so-called rational logic of development. Which, in the end, is racist, violent, genocidal, murderous. It aims to clear the territory for the advancement of soybeans.”***

(SB member from Local community & Academia)

Story F. Peatland degradation in the Netherlands as a consequence of intensive livestock farming. Peatland moss are active witnesses of soy histories and their repercussions. The Peatland moss “records all of the different things that humans do to that specific landscape. (...) it records the excessive amount of nutrients. That is, animal farming, and by extension, what soy farming brings to this area.”

“I am part of Soy Stories³, a project which investigates connected histories of soybeans in the Netherlands and Brazil. And within that project, I am doing a PhD study that investigates soy histories in different landscapes in the Netherlands and, next year, also in Brazil. I still have to figure out what exactly I'm going to do. So that's really exciting. That's why I'm really excited to meet different soy researchers.

*Maybe just for context, I am an environmental historian. That means **I am interested in how humans and the environment have interacted in the past. And how we can understand the environment as sort of an active participant in histories.** I'm very passionate about this approach because I think it's very valuable to rethink how the environment was always present in all human histories. And in that way, it might serve us to reimagine some of the present and futures that we envision. But having said that, as a historian, I'm not super good at translating my research into action. Or ideas for policy interventions. Which is also why I'm very excited to learn more from you guys. On how to do that, right? (...)*

This is the picture that I picked. You can see it in half of my screen. It is from my research in the Netherlands at the moment. It is a degraded peatland⁴ that I am researching in relation to the history of the expansion of intensive livestock farming that relies heavily on imported feed stuff.

³ More information about the Soy Stories project can be found here:

<https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/research-institutes/athena-institute/more-about/soy-stories>

<https://www.soystories.info/>

⁴ “Peatlands are terrestrial wetland ecosystems in which waterlogged conditions prevent plant material from fully decomposing. Consequently, the production of organic matter exceeds its decomposition, which results in a net accumulation of peat.” Source: International Peatland Society (<https://peatlands.org/peatlands/what-are-peatlands/>)

Picture 8. Peatland moss in the Netherlands.

*I am showing this picture because I took it when I was conducting an oral history interview with an environmental activist who picked this **tiny part of peatland moss** for me to show me how **it records all of the different things that humans do to that specific landscape.***

*And one of them is that **it records the excessive amount of nutrients. That is, animal farming, and by extension, soy farming brings to this area. And this causes...** This brings this tiny little peatland, which at first sight, like it's somewhere in the remote Netherlands, might have nothing to do with **this whole story, but it kind of shows how those broader commodity chains entangle various communities in their problems.** And how also communities that do not define their problems in relation to soybeans are still affected by the histories that have created this.*

This specific environmental activist is changing, and she/he has explained a whole change (in the activists') strategy. They are trying to protect, how they're defining the borders of what they are trying to achieve, and how they are relating to other places through the changing materialities that they are finding in the peatland. I think that it is very interesting! It is a small insight into what I am researching here.

I really hope that I can transfer this type of research to a Brazilian case study at some point to show what happens on the edges of so expansion. So, not to be so involved with the histories of the kind of big actors, but to figure out who else became entangled with the history of soy production.

(...) The main insights that we keep having is that there are so many alternatives and knowledges that kind of get lost along the way. Then we end up with a present situation that seems super inevitable. So, I think part of the change that I want to achieve with my research is to contribute to a kind of more nuanced understanding of the present, and to make sure that it wasn't, it's not understood as logical or inevitable that it is to be played out in this way."

(SB member from Academia)

Story G. Mosquitoes and a plant-based natural repellent in connection to soy. Soy farming feeds beef exporting industries in Southern Brazil. The widespread use of “agrochemicals in crop plantation, and the waste, the residues of the meat production” are “leaking into the rivers. The fish is unable to survive, (...) and a lot of mosquitoes proliferate.”

“I am also a Ph.D. candidate in the Soy Stories project. I basically tackle the Brazilian part of the project. (...) For contextualization, well, let me show you this photo. You can see a hand holding a spray bottle. And it has a homemade repellent inside. I think it was made out with Citronella and lemongrass. And a lot of different kind of plants mixtures. But this was taken during our first visit or first experimental field work in Brazil, November last year. And we are visiting an experimental area of a public university in the Southern part of Brazil.

Despite the repellent, we suffered a lot of mosquito bites that day, in a time span of 10 minutes or so.

As someone super allergic to mosquito bites, my ankles felt up quite badly. And I had a painful itchiness for several days. Carol and I actually to be honest. We even joked about how we were like giving our blood to the project, quite literally. but it was "disappearance" that really got me thinking: why are there so many mosquitoes in that area? Because I'm also from the South of Brazil. And I have never seen so many before.

Picture 9. Mosquito repellent made of Citronella, Lemongrass and a mixture of other plants, Southern Brazil.

Well, it turns out that in that region, the farmers (that are mostly small farmers), they produce soybeans primarily for internal use, for internal consumption of the meat industry. The city in which we were is also a major producer of pork and chicken meat for international markets. The widespread agrochemicals that they use in the crop plantation and the waste, the residues of the meat production in that city are leaking into the rivers, polluting the rivers. The fish is unable to survive, of course that is toxic water. And because of that (the disappearance of the fish), a lot of mosquitoes are able to proliferate in an uncontrollable way.

We did a lot of different kinds of interviews, with different kinds of actors, in that city as well. The interests of small farmers and the cooperatives working with soybeans is basically only detaining certifications. Especially when they heard that we are working within a university in the Netherlands. What they really want to know is what the Netherlands wants from them. What the Netherlands expects from them to really facilitate the trade, the markets trade. They actually don't care about these kinds of things that we had just experienced, right?

*I am also quite bad at thinking about actions, to be honest, as a researcher. And here comes the contextualization. I have a background in dance studies. I have my bachelor's degree and Dance, but also studied Marketing for three years at an academic level. **One thing that really interests me is the idea of storytelling or "story selling."** Because right now marketing campaigns, or propaganda, really like use the storytelling in order to sell it. So, they do know the profile of the consumers, right?*

*What I would like to propose as a change is the idea of us researchers really doing the move of **reshaping the way that we tell our stories. Really focus on the consumers, or not only the consumers, but the audience we focus on. The public.** I do think it is important for us to understand other realities, of course, but in this individualistic and capitalistic societies that will lead, we are mostly affected and really influenced by things that affect us. This is why I think that we should shape our stories based on our audiences, and the things that affect them."*

(SB member from Academia)

Story H. A story about the farming system in the Netherlands, the Schiphol airport, and the sectors that can kick start the change in the system: finance, food and retail sectors!

"I've got two pictures because I couldn't choose. This is the first one. And this is the second one, and I'll leave this one open. You can see me here (Picture 10) when I was still young, and I was still doing my PhD. So, maybe let's start there. So, who am I? I am now a campaigner and analyst for the NGO Friends of the Earth. For two months, so, I am quite new in this job. Until quite recently, I was working as a researcher, an assistant professor in food studies at the University of Amsterdam. Working on sustainable land use. Actually, when you showed me the leverage points picture, it is funny because I was teaching about that until very recently. But yeah, this is me much younger when I was still starting my PhD.

*As you know, there is a housing crisis in Amsterdam, so I couldn't find a house. Instead, I ended up renting a room on a farm. Well as you can see, quite close to the Schiphol airport. **It is a wide-open area, all these farms. Well, actually, the area itself used to be a lake not even 150 years ago. So, it is all completely artificial lands here. And it's all square, so highly intensive. Very industrialized, and this is now a potato farm.***

Picture 10. Potato farm in the Netherlands in the surroundings of the Schiphol airport.

Note: we covered the face in the pic for the sake of anonymization.

*The Schiphol airport is there as well, which is one of the biggest airports now in in the world. So, the farmers I used to live with, one of them is 65 years old. I think they're sort of survivors of this system we are in. **The system where you must become bigger and grow or you will go bankrupt. And many of them do (go bankrupt) in the Netherlands. So that's that explains to me why there is only one way forward for farmers in the Netherlands. In the potato industry, yes, but also in the livestock industry: it is to grow bigger and bigger, more intensive.***

*Another thing about **this farmer** is that, yeah, he is 65 years old now. He is battling leukemia for a while now. And I always kind of wondered, because you can't prove this, but I was always wondering like: is it because of the pesticides? Is it because of Schiphol airport, which is next doors? What is it? And then that that's kind of really. Sad to think about.*

The whole Schiphol airport meanwhile is trying to get the land so they're trying to acquire. Sometimes, you know, somewhat threatening and forceful way they are trying to acquire this land of the farmer. So far not successful, but I think it's only a matter of time.

Picture 11. Amsterdam Schiphol airport potential expansion threatening farmer's land.

*The point here is these farmers, while they are industrial scale farmers, I think they're not to blame for that. They were just surviving in the only way you could survive. **My fear is that this system is now being exported, or is already exported across the world, and also to Brazil. This way of working with the lands which somehow makes sense in the Netherlands, where everything is artificial, the farming is also somewhat industrial and artificial, but you don't have to export it everywhere.** And that's what I really fear. That we are losing all this diversity. And instead, we are only going to get one style of standard farm, the same across the world. And that's just sad.*

*Then coming to what I want to change them. I want not to blame these farmers or the livestock farmers, even the mega stable livestock farmers. **I want to draw the attention as much as possible to the financial institutions, like the big banks that are creating a system where you can only survive in one very particular, very intensive, very industrial way.** I want to blame and do something with, or against, the industrial, the food industry, the agro industry.*

*That is, is in the same way also, **narrowing what it what the possibilities and the range of possibilities for farmers. So, regulate them as much as possible.** Also here in the Netherlands, I think **we need to start thinking about, we must not just think about, but we must decrease our animal protein consumption dramatically. So, eat less animals. We must do this, I think, faster than the rest of the world, because of justice. Climate justice reasons.***

*And again, then you could say, ok, **this is up to the consumers, but I don't think so. Again, I think you should always look up to where the money is. And in this case, for example, with protein consumption, this is the supermarkets. They can change this, and we must regulate them. That's my story.***

(SB member from NGO & Academia)

Systems Mapping

Based on the stories from the previous section, and our research on the case study so far, the chart below illustrates our systems map (onion diagram), which includes some of the different factors influencing our case study (key system).

Chart 1. Map with key systems including factors affecting the case trade

Table 3. Some key relationships between factors emerging from the stories

<p>Ecological</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species with high ecosystem value (e.g. peatlands in the Netherlands, which are carbon sinkers and biodiversity hotspots) threatened by intensive farming • Animals lose their habitats and migrate to cities in Cerrado
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dairy industry in the Netherlands highly dependent on only few species (e.g., Holstein Friesian cattle; and English ryegrass for feeding), preventing variety, and representing monocultures.
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial sector is a lock-in protecting the conventional production system; it prevents farmers to transition to agroecological production models • Agro chemicals/Pesticide MNCs profit from conventional intensive farming system • Retailers and consumers have power to change consumption patterns, especially in the Netherlands • Trading companies (e.g., Cargil, AMD, Bunge, etc.) profit from conventional production & trade of soy and beef, and can hinder changes towards a more sustainable model • Alternative production models (e.g., ecological tourism in the Amazon/Cerrado) could bring development without intensive soy & beef farming
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local peoples, communities and ecosystems poisoned by pesticides in the Amazon and Cerrado • Resistances to agribusiness expansion/trade exist to both in Brazil's Amazon and Cerrado (Indigenous, peasants, Afro-descendants, women, etc.) and in the Netherlands (NGOs, agroecology farmers, etc.).
Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social movements pressure governments to change Free-trade agreements and policies (e.g., CAP) • EUDR should align with national policies (Brazil, Netherlands), but voices of marginalised groups have yet to be heard in re-assessing the regulation

Leverage Points

The stories presented in the workshop demonstrate different possibilities of transformations for better prioritising biodiversity at different levels of change (intra-personal, inter-personal, and/or institutional).

Inspired by these stories, we discussed, also during the workshop, the Leverage Points (LPs) more closely associated with each of the interventions (for transformative change) highlighted in each story. The table below summarizes what was shared in each story, considering in particular the “post its” written by participants in the *Miro Board*, but also the comments during the plenary session. Each story, aligned with interventions and leverage

point, proposes a unique narrative of change. In later stages of the case study, we can potentially delve deeper into these stories, in connection with other research outputs (interviews, lit reviews, etc.), to propose an integrated narrative of change for the case study.

Table 4. Interventions and Leverage Points emerging from the stories

Story	Intervention(s)	LPs
A Children and rural development in the Cerrado. Concretely, more access to companies' sourcing polygons. On a deeper level, the development of rural areas through alternative production systems.	Intervention 1: Public sharing of commodity origination/polygon data (anonymized/aggregated)	LPs associated with Intervention 2: Valuing forest people's socio-biodiversity value chains
	Who starts: Companies Who else participates: Government, Civil society, Local communities	MATERIAL -Access to the adequate technology
	Intervention 2: Valuing forest people's socio-biodiversity value chains	PROCESSES -Subsidies -Access to markets
		DESIGN -Support of the public sector to value chains of socio-biodiversity products
		INTENT Strengthen the understanding that a full life comes from health, peace and abundance rather than the accumulation of capital
		In order to: Make it possible to value agricultural production oriented towards the health and nutrition of people and the environment
Story B Macaws in urban Brasília, visitors or victims from habitat loss? <i>Chapada dos Veadeiros</i> national park and soy plantations "right on the edge" of the protected area.	Valuing the preservation of native vegetation and biodiversity Who starts: Government, Companies, Civil society Who else participates: Government	MATERIAL -Reduce the volumes (of soy and beef) exported -Reduce the planted areas -Improvement in transport and storage logistics to avoid losses and waste
		PROCESSES -Political willingness -Investments -Engagement of producers
		DESIGN -Payment for ecosystem services -Expansion of existing regulations for the Amazon to include the Cerrado -Carbon credits
		INTENT -A change in values about progress and development
C Mobilizing against trade agreements that support	Reform of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Who starts: EU Commission	MATERIAL -Reduce amount of soy imported to Europe/Netherlands

<p>large scale farming. Moving towards agroecology and food sovereignty.</p>	<p>Who else participates: Social movements and Peasant's organisations</p>	<p>PROCESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Political climate (rise of the extreme right in Europe) -Group of new farmers wanting to move towards agroecology -Ability of social movements to articulate -Citizens's awareness of soy problematic
		<p>DESIGN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reform Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) to stop subsidy for agri-business and industrial agriculture and to support agroecology and small-scale farming
		<p>INTENT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Move from intensive and export-oriented paradigm towards agroecological paradigm that respects nature, respects the rights of peasants all over the world and that is based on solidarity between the Global South and North
<p>D</p> <p>Amazon schoolteachers and students poisoned by soy agrottoxins. Cattle farming amid a lonely Chesnutt tree, "as if the tree could live without the forest that surrounds it." We need another type of involvement with the forest!</p>	<p>Tackling air pollution caused by agrottoxins in Santarém (Amazon)</p> <p>Who starts: Soy Companies Who else participates: State Public Prosecutor's Office; Local networks of activists</p>	<p>MATERIAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Gradual reduction of soy plantations in the region
		<p>PROCESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Lack of information from local society about the real problems caused by agricultural pesticides -Inform the local population about the value of land, not the price imposed on the economic system
		<p>DESIGN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Communication to the international public about the real problems caused by soy -Technological innovation to agroforestry products -Brazil stopping to import agrottoxins which are forbidden in other countries
<p>E</p> <p>Environmental racism. "When Cargill operations were set up in the region, they destroyed the local beach called <i>Vera Paz</i>," a space for popular leisure activities. They argued that it was "a beach for the poor, black, and vagabond." This shows how agribusiness' "rational logic of development" is actually "racist, violent,</p>	<p>A documentary/film about soy-driven environmental racism in Santarém (Amazon)</p> <p>Who starts: Quilombola Federation; Indigenous Counsel of the Santarem Plateau; CITA</p> <p>Who else participates: International organizations; State Public Prosecutor's Office; NGOs; Human rights organizations</p>	<p>MATERIAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Structure for documentary production: -Digital camera -Tripod -Recorder and microphone -Headphones -Lighting
		<p>PROCESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Access to Financing. -Partnership with NGOs
		<p>DESIGN</p> <p>---</p>

<p>genocidal,” aiming to clear the territory to open the space for soy.</p>		<p>INTENT ---</p>
<p>F</p> <p>Petland degradation in the Netherlands as a consequence of intensive livestock farming. Petland moss are active witnesses of soy histories and their repercussions. The Petland moss “records all of the different things that humans do to that specific landscape. (...) it records the excessive amount of nutrients. That is, animal farming, and by extension, what soy farming brings to this area.”</p>	<p>Intervention 1: Understanding historical perspectives on soy-based agriculture and how it changed spatial and temporal imaginations of different landscapes;</p> <p>Intervention 2: Bring historical perspectives into public debates/cultural imagination</p> <p>Who starts: preferably communities themselves with support of researchers; Cultural institutions, rituals, education institutes have a role to play in how we envision the world and what knowledge humans carry into them.</p> <p>Who else participates: politicians would profit from long-term perspectives</p>	<p>Intervention 2: Bring historical perspectives into public debates/cultural imagination</p> <p>MATERIAL - Stop imagination of inevitability of soy-based agriculture (imaginings of unending frontiers, growth, detachment from environmental conditions).</p> <p>PROCESSES - Build up vocabulary to intervene - Stop structurally underfunding the humanities</p> <p>DESIGN -Changes in education - Environment and environmental health not as a given precondition to education or cultural output.</p> <p>INTENT - Multiplicities of history material and more-than-human agency of the environment - Move beyond non-linear interpretations of history (highlight contingencies of history)</p>
<p>G</p> <p>Mosquitoes and a plant-based natural repellent in connection to soy. Soy farming feeds beef exporting industries in Southern Brazil. The widespread use of “agrochemicals in crop plantation, and the waste, the residues of the meat production” are “leaking into the rivers. The fish is unable to survive, (...) and a lot of mosquitoes proliferate.”</p>	<p>Shape (soy & beef) stories according to different audiences</p> <p>Who starts: Researchers/academia</p> <p>Who else participates: Diverse actors that inform our research, being affected by and/or affecting the soybean chain, for example. Media outlets</p>	<p>MATERIAL - What kind of knowledges should we include or exclude from our stories?</p> <p>PROCESSES - How can the circulation of these stories, reshaped to address specific audiences, can permeate new narratives and imaginaries? - More avenues, outside academic ones, to open communication</p> <p>DESIGN - How can, from audience focused stories, can we open up discussions on the inclusion/exclusion of others? - Moving from the "self" to "others"</p> <p>INTENT - The formative role of these stories in affecting perceptions AND practices -Coexistences</p>
<p>H</p> <p>A story about the farming system in the Netherlands, the Schiphol airport, and the sectors that can kick start the change in the system:</p>	<p>Intervention 1: Deforestation financing ban (Regulate banks and agribusiness)</p> <p>Who starts: EU Who else participates: Other regions (esp. Brazil).</p> <p>**</p>	<p>LPs for Intervention 1: Deforestation financial ban</p> <p>MATERIAL Stop money flow to deforestation</p> <p>PROCESSES ---</p> <p>DESIGN - Develop robust deforestation ban in bank portfolios - Increase transparency in global supply chains</p>

finance, food and retail sectors!	Intervention 2: Reduce share of animal proteins in food supply Who starts: Supermarkets Who else participates: Other value chain actors	INTENT - Environmental justice as leading paradigm
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Source: notes produced by participants during the workshop. Miro Boards:

<https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVK41pCuA=/>

<https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVK3F7hgk=/>

Monitoring & Indicators

Table 5. Some indicators to monitor the interventions proposed in the stories

Story/Intervention(s)/Specific action	Indicators
B/Valuing the preservation of native vegetation and biodiversity	<p>1) Expansion of existing regulations for the Amazon to include the Cerrado (other wooded lands) – more restricted EUDR / Forest Code/ Expansion of the Soy Moratorium - Indicator related to monitoring legislation - Indicator to monitor the growth in the area covered by the Soy Moratorium - Indicator of number of producers who opt for preservation despite having the possibility of legally deforesting</p> <p>2) Payment for ecosystem services (PES) - Indicators of growth in the number of recipients of PES - Indicators of the amounts of money received</p> <p>3) Carbon credits - Indicator: level of access for small, medium and large producers to participate in carbon credit projects</p>
C/ Reform of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)	1) Monitor the quantity of resources (\$) allocated to small agroecology farmers
D/ Tackling air pollution caused by agrotoxins in Santarém (Amazon)	<p>1) Inter-crossing data for a given geographical space. More holistic understanding of interlocking impacts of soy production & livestock farming & deforestation & mining & etc. (other socio-environmental phenomena in the region) as co-constitutive, not isolated processes.</p> <p>How to produce: research institutes (e.g., Fiocruz, academia), but also other types of organisations</p> <p><u>Comments during plenary:</u> Connected with concept of Sacrifice Zones, & environmental (in)justice/intersectionality</p>
H/ Intervention 1: Deforestation financing ban (Regulate banks and agribusiness) / Regulate the financial sector	1) Proposal from the European Commission on regulation of the financial sector (foreseen in EUDR review 2024 and CSDDD in a few years)

	<p>2) Adoption of regulation in the EU under the European Union Deforestation or CSDDD that prohibits the financing of deforestation, forest degradation and related human rights violations</p> <p>3) Adoption in other regions of regulations to prevent waterbed effect with priority for rules in Brazil for Brazilian banks and investors (green taxonomy expected this year).</p>
<p>H/ Intervention 1: Deforestation financing ban (Regulate banks and agribusiness) / Develop new financial instruments for agro-ecology and community forest management</p>	<p>1) NGO Defund Deforestation coalitions develop stronger Finance for Solutions workstreams and reach out to policy makers</p> <p>2) Public finance for agriculture shift towards agro-ecology and community forest management in line with CBD targets and defunds harmful sectors</p> <p>3) New financial products and organisations gain visibility and scale</p>
<p>H/ Intervention 2: Reduce share of animal proteins in food supply/ Reduce meat consumption</p>	<p>1) Level of consumption of meat in EU</p> <p>2) Adopted policies to reduce meat intake and processed foods, for example in ready-made meals</p>
<p>H/ Intervention 2: Reduce share of animal proteins in food supply/ Stop expansion of industrial livestock sector</p>	<p>1) Number of industrial farms in EU</p> <p>2) Volume importation of soy for feedstock industrial farms</p> <p>3) Growth in agro-ecological farms</p> <p>4) Policies to halt expansion of industrial farms and number of animals</p>

Barriers & Opportunities for Broader Change

In Table 6, the broader impacts presented are not organized by order of story (A, B, C...F), but according to the order in which they appeared in the discussion. This preserves the flow of the discussion, allowing us to observe which comment/topic/point triggered (paved the way for) the emergence of the subsequent comment/topic/point raised.

Table 6. Some indicators to monitor the interventions proposed in the stories

Story/Intervention(s)	Broader Impacts
<p>B/Valuing the preservation of native vegetation and biodiversity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntary sustainability standards that strengthen the focus on the social/human rights dimensions. • More effective and truly inclusive inter-stakeholders' dialogues (beyond the formal procedure). <p><u>Comments during plenary:</u> A documentary (film) is a practical intervention that can contribute to more effective dialogues. Because it allows different stakeholders to engage (and truly include) local communities. A potential barrier for this is that territories</p>

	<p>such as in Santarém become more violent inasmuch as far right politics advances (locally and globally).</p> <p><i>“Agribusiness has a very strong public campaign in Brazil and in Santarém, right? “Agro is pop”, “Agro is this, agro is that.” And we have a very vulnerable population. I saw a statistic recently here in the Santarém region, that in the urban area, 65% of people earn up to 800 reais. 65% of people earn up to 800 reais. In other words, people are not eating properly, people are hungry, people are eating sausages, salty foods, canned foods, poor quality processed food, which will cause diseases. So, any speech about more income, employment, development, ends up capturing people. So, you have, for example, at UFOPA, teachers who start agribusiness research are intimidated, even by students in the classroom, because they believe that this is the only way to develop the region, right? So, we have a fight that is symbolic, a cultural fight with the media, with advertising.”</i></p>
<p>D/ Tackling air pollution caused by agrottoxins in Santarém (Amazon)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The local perception of people in Santarém in that the soy exported to China goes to the livestock sector and for human feed; whereas the soy directed to the EU goes in particular the livestock sector/animal feed. <p><u>Comments during plenary:</u></p> <p>Reducing soy imported by the EU from Brazil will not solve the socio-environmental issues in Brazil, because soy would be sent to China. Issue of leakage.</p> <p>Around 15% of Brazilian soy is exported to the EU. But the % that goes to China is much higher.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slave labour not common in the soy sector, but in the livestock sector in Brazil. However, the soy sector has a condition of semi-slavery (non-use of PPE in soy farming). <p><u>Comments during plenary:</u></p> <p><i>“My perception is that slave labour in Brazil, it is much more concentrated on livestock farming. In relation to soy, I believe that most of the problems with regard to labour issues would not be slave labour, but rather the violation of human rights, because the activity of soy farming, with this heritage of the green revolution, does not employ so much, right?”</i></p> <p><i>But we see, for example, I’ve had a student, it’s a technical school, where I teach young people and adults, a soybean transport driver, who didn’t use any Personal Protective Equipment (PPE). He said it himself, so there is direct contamination. If it’s a more critical analysis for me, this is environmental racism at work, right?”</i></p> <p><i>In other words, it is also semi-slavery, since the person is not being instructed to use PPE, because that is what happens locally, also because a company is a multinational trading company, it is directly linked to the exploitation of local people working in soy plantations, who take this soy and then exports it.</i></p> <p><i>So, a company can say that it brings “clean soy” (to the EU), but whoever has a health problem in the production place, the company says that is has nothing to do with it, right? If there is slave labour, you have disrespect for labour standards and the use of personal protective equipment.”</i></p>
<p>H/ Intervention 1: Deforestation financing ban (Regulate banks and agribusiness) & Intervention 2: Reduce share of animal proteins in food supply</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The production and consumption of oil crops is highly globalised. This means that if less soy is produced and the demand for oil crops is not reduced, other countries will take over the production with soy or other oil crops. • The crops are largely interchangeable and substitutable. Currently almost 40% of agriculture crop land is for oil crops, and this is expected to increase.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The increase in demand is because world meat consumption continues to rise as well as industrial applications, specifically for biofuels. We do need production to reduce the ‘fat gap’ in various African countries. • The trade is highly concentrated: only a few big traders such as Bunge, Wilmar determine the price and volumes as well as production standards. • The expansion of oil crops has always been driven by finance including national banks, state capital as this is a highly profitable sector. • A massive substitution of traditional sources of food and feed took place, for example replacing coconut oil for cooking and waste materials for feed by soy and palm. • Oil crops are cheap, they are highly industrialised, advanced crop varieties, byproducts are capitalised and the market has been competitive and has benefited from government support. • Therefore, alternative production systems face many challenges to grow, and it is key that we REDUCE consumption of vegetable oil products and CREATE POLICIES for enabling environments to promote community-based agriculture and forest management for strong local economies and food sovereignty
<p>G/ Shape (soy & beef) stories according to different audiences</p>	<p><u>Comments during plenary:</u></p> <p><i>“I wasn't thinking in a really specific sector, but when I was trying to think I was, I think I even wrote in one of the the boards, something like moving the discussions from the self to others. So there's recognition of the other as a coexistent being or even like the recognition in order to discuss things right? Because if you don't recognise the other as someone that you can discuss, the dialogue will never be open.”</i></p> <p>Question from one participant from Academia: In your Ph.D. thesis that you are going to write, do you plan to write a normal thesis, or do you foresee the stories there?</p> <p>Reply from the author of story G:</p> <p><i>“I guess it's quite difficult because we are both in Science technology departments. I'm the Department of Industrial Engineering and Innovation Sciences. So it is quite difficult to go outside of the pre given format. Here we usually work with article basis. So five articles that composes one thesis. (...) So, what we are trying to do, at least from my side, I really try to replace at least one article with something else, perhaps a documentary, perhaps a performance, but it is quite difficult.”</i></p>
<p>F/ Intervention 1: Understanding historical perspectives on soy-based agriculture and how it changed spatial and temporal imaginations of different landscapes.</p> <p>&</p> <p>Intervention 2: Bring historical perspectives into public debates/cultural imagination.</p>	<p><u>Comments during plenary:</u></p> <p>Question from one participant from Academia: In your Ph.D. thesis that you are going to write, do you plan to write a normal thesis, or do you foresee the stories there?</p> <p>Reply from the author of story F:</p> <p><i>“I'm in the same situation. It is also super difficult. On the one hand, I want to establish myself as a sort of scholar to be taken seriously in my fields, and I want to do something new. And I also want to do something with multiple audiences. And I'm navigating all of these institutional restrictions, so it is difficult to do that. I'll also staying healthy and producing something that can be finished within four years. I think for now, what I'm trying to do is, yeah, I'm trying to develop field research methods that can help bring multiple voices into conversation and we'll see how that goes or whether I can succeed at that. And yeah, by trying to develop multi-sided research, as in my case, I think that's</i></p>

	<i>really important to figure out how stories from various places can be mobilised to challenge each other.”</i>
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Conclusion & Reflections

In the Wrap Up session during workshop application in June 25, Cristina Inoue posed the following question:

*“I have a question. (...) It seems to me that we have to put it in different universes or different pluriverses. Maybe both Leonardo and Mike and João from certain media outlets so on the cutting edge, on the local edges. Like that, right? You have already seen peasant movements in Holland, which has a characteristic. I went to that La Via Campesina conference, right? The configuration there is very different, but there is the thing about being there, right? On the front line. And Mike there on the other end. **What do you think people at the university can do to help?** That's where we are. We are not in the government. I'm not in an NGO, for example. So, **what can we do, from our positions as university professors, researchers, to support the local peoples' causes, communities, movements?**”*

Participants replied to the question as follows.

Workshop Participant 1 (member from civil society & academia, Santarém, Pará, Brazil):

“We had an experience in 2002, 2003, when Cargill was setting up shop here and helping to finance the land acquisition process, right? We established a relationship with Banco do Brasil and then many small producers started selling their lands, thinking that BRL 40,000, at the time BRL 50,000, was enough to live on in Santarém.

In the case of the outskirts of the cities that fell into extreme poverty, we managed to create a large support network, right? With social movements, international organizations, and, at that time, Greenpeace came in. Here we managed to establish good connections because Greenpeace did good political propaganda, and we even managed to put the brakes on Cargill.

But later we disagreed, we disagreed with this alliance politically because there came a certain point when some organizations, like Greenpeace, for example, especially Greenpeace, which was the main one, also ended up convincing some leaders that it was possible to legalize soy. And we were part of a movement that said: there should be no soybeans here in the Amazon. Let's invest in something else, such as tourism, in production that doesn't involve legalized soybeans.

*This divided the movement and Cargill ended up consolidating itself here, right? But even though we didn't achieve a victory, we managed to make a lot of progress, right? With international communication. **I think that creating this international network and I think that the debate now is about environmental justice and environmental racism. I think that's the approach we have to take from now on.***

The comment above illustrates the dynamics between local social movements in articulation with international networks, to promote resistance against soy expansion in the Amazon (Santarém region). The comment exemplifies challenges for these partnerships to survive over time. Despite the lack of success of the partnership, as exemplified in the comment, the possibility of such partnerships and networks is considered important by the respective Workshop Participant 1 (from civil society & academia, Santarém, Pará, Brazil), which is a local activist. The relevance of these alliances resides in the fact that they raise awareness about local challenges to promote sustainable development, prioritise biodiversity and people. One such challenge nowadays is the fight against environmental racism.

Workshop Participant 2 (representative from the civil society organization *La Via Campesina*, The Netherlands) replied to Cristina's question as follows:

*"I'll say it quickly, I agree with everything that was said. I also think it's **very important for universities to provide a space for rural producers, and perhaps other traditional peoples as well, to be heard, right?** I really miss that, because there could be more of that voice in universities.*

*But another thing that has already been mentioned is **to do projects together, right?** We have, **we need resources and there are a lot of things that we could do together, right?** Experimenting with agricultural practices. This issue of access to land, environmental racism, these are issues that **we could work on together and create a partnership in a network, which could also continue in the long term, right?** Because projects always end, sometimes they last 2 years, sometimes they last 4 years and then they end, but it would be good to keep going and build something together. That would help more."*

The comment reiterates the relevance of NGOs working together with universities and local communities to build collaborative networks to implement projects. For example, co-developing/co-creating and reflecting about agricultural practices that promote access to land while opposing environmental racism.

In the Wrap Up session during workshop application in June 28, a Workshop Participant 3 (representative from academia in the Netherlands) commented:

*"[...] **we should be so careful on what kind of stories we should address. What kind of stories we should tell, what kind of stories should we shed light on. Because if I may share a quick example.***

I was investigating the idea that the mainstream narrative that indigenous people are affected negatively by soybeans. It is a given, when you were talking about Brazil and soybeans. But then sometimes you stumble upon some examples that show indigenous communities that actually want to plant soybeans in indigenous lands. When we went to the South, to do field work in Brazil, we found out that that's a reality of actually a lot of indigenous communities that want to plant soybeans.

*But how to portray that story, in a way that is not instrumentalized by the big corporations? And like subverted, you know, so they say like "great! Let's plant soy on indigenous land." Some indigenous peoples actually want to plant soy. So, **how to tell those "in between stories," without offering these narratives to people in power?** I think it's super difficult."*

Another Workshop Participant 4 (representative from academia in Brazil) replied to that:

*"I would like also to know more about what goes on in in regions of soy production. **When I look at, for instance, political representation there. Because agribusiness is extremely strong, and it only benefits some people. But most people, as in all of Brazil, are still poor. But they vote for people who come from the agribusiness sector very much***

So, how they do politics? I know there's a lot of historical inequalities and flaws in the democracy that persists until today. So, if you've got money, you can get elected.

*I'm interested in those **processes about how at the local level, the political representatives [coming from the agribusiness sector] get elected there. And how they end up not only in the local level, but also in Congress in Brazil. I think that if the Parliamentary Front was a political party, It would actually have a majority by itself. It could govern by itself in Congress and make laws by itself. [...]. So, how do these political power structures become reproduced at the local level?**"*

The Workshop Participant 3 comment highlights the need to be careful about the stories we share, and how to share them, to avoid providing input that can be potentially used by powerful groups to promote soy agriculture on Indigenous peoples' lands. On a different direction, Niels's comment suggests the need to further investigate why agribusiness-related politicians receive so much popular support (e.g., in voting) in soy regions, such as in the Amazon and in the Cerrado.

All the comments and suggestions presented by SB members are being considered in our research, but it does not mean that we have the capacity or objective of following all of them strictly. These stories and reflections are valuable inputs in our ongoing conversation with SB members in the course of our research in the Trade case study, informing our research and actions.

